

***HOW COMICS TRAVEL: PUBLICATION, TRANSLATION, RADICAL LITERACIES*, KATHERINE KELP-STEBBINS, (2022)**

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Reviewed by Ian Gordon, National University of Singapore

It is refreshing to read a book that goes big on the argument for comics. Katherine Kelp-Stebbins “contends that comics provide alternative mapping tools and methods for reading the world in its mutability” (p. 1). The book is a work of theory and the core point for me is that comics are not universal and might not “travel” as well or as easily as we imagine. Old historian that I am, I have not had to work so hard at understanding theory since grad school, when I participated in a weekly gathering that had Kaja Silverman and Mieke Bal as core participants. But friends of a theoretical bent found *How Comics Travel* easy enough to comprehend. Kelp-Stebbins comes to comics from a background in post-colonial theory and her approach is that of a comparativist. Her work focuses then on the varied systems and circuits of power that produce comics and graphic novels and indeed establish global canons.

Kelp-Stebbins provides five case studies of the way authors, artists, publishers, translators, and readers manifested comics in different locales and at different times. The first of these evocatively titled, “The Adventures of Three Readers in the World of Tintin,” analyses the way Tintin constructs different worlds for different readers across time and space. She takes as her subjects Scott McCloud, the well-known American comics artist and theorist, Bienvenu Mbutu Mondondo, a Congolese émigré to Belgium, and Charles Burns, another familiar US comics artist. Through this study Kelp-Stebbins demonstrates that “the coloniality of Tintin in the Congo is not reducible to its content; it is a fulfilment of the complex of visuality by which the content is

instrumentalized. By melding verbal and visual regimes and normalizing the disjuncture between fanciful images and the historical plenitude of toponyms and "petit negre," *Tintin au Congo* produces a graphically novel colonial reading subject" (pp. 48-49).

In her second chapter Kelp-Stebbin examines Magdy El Shafee's *Metro* and the various international editions that appeared after the original was banned in Egypt. In discussing the problems of translation she notes that all texts are translatable because they "can be interpreted." But comics pose particular issues because they are a mix of images and words and some of these are simply not translatable. Kelp-Stebbins highlights "the commingling of word and image" as a root cause of much of these issues (p. 75). A work of fiction *Metro* none the less dealt in Egyptian realities and at least one figure in the book bore a close resemblance to a public figure which led to the work being confiscated and banned (p. 77). Picked up outside Egypt in various countries the work for a time was more circulated outside the country in various translations than within Egypt. The matter of translating a visual representation that suggested a well-known public figure, too successfully in the original, into other languages is rather impossible. How would non-Egyptian audiences recognize such a figure and the implications of the representation? Kelp-Stebbins unpacks how issues such as this led to wildly different versions of *Metro* across different languages.

In her third chapter Kelp-Stebbins addresses the production and reception complexities of Marjane Satrapi's *Persepolis*. There are so many factors at play in this graphic novel that understanding it necessitates something well beyond a nuanced reading. For Kelp-Stebbins it is a mistake to describe a person of Iranian birth, but

working in France and within French comics traditions, as an East to West translator (p. 104). *Persepolis* must be one of the most misunderstood comics of all times. Kelp-Stebbins list a series of different takes on the work:

Readers have called *Persepolis* “feminist” (Chute, “Retracing” 94), “humanizing” (Whitlock, *Soft Weapons* 189), “self-aggrandizing” (Singer 154), “didactic” (Place-Verghnes 258), “Iranian exilic” (Malek 354), “the first Iranian comic book” (N. Miller 15), “full of traces of the globalism of the Persian miniature aesthetic” (Ostby 568), “very Western” (Bahrapour), “avant garde” (Chute “Retracing” 99), “draw[ing] on an ancient and transnational precedent” (Ostby 560), “nation-centered . . . yet thoroughly global” (Ostby 562), “democratic” (Mazhari 290), “postcolonial” (Naghibi and O’Malley 235), “a mosaic of Middle Eastern and Western” (Hajdu), “complicat[ing] the simplistic scripts Westerners have assigned to the region labeled ‘the Middle East’” (Tensuan 952), “neoliberal” (Singer 154), and “beyond a global, neoliberal agenda” (Gilmore 157) (p. 108).

Her criticism here is directed at seeing *Persepolis* as an Eastern text making an impact on a monolithic West, rather than a Western text from France making an impact in translation in the USA. Building on Bart Beaty’s work in *Unpopular Culture* Kelp-Stebbins notes that “the relevant question is not how did *Persepolis* come from Iran to the West but, instead, how did this text reached particular readers in France and the US at distinctive moments in time? (p. 110).” Kelp-Stebbins finds this moment in the comparisons made between Satrapi and Art Spiegelman. The era of *Persepolis*’s arrival and impact in America was the era of comics “not just for kids anymore” and the autobiographical comic becoming a leading form in the emerging graphical novel

market. Indeed, *Persepolis* has become a key work in a canon of comics that require another name and if graphic novel doesn't quite capture memoirs in the comic form then neologisms like autographical (not a word that Kelp-Stebbins uses) lend them intellectual heft.

In her fourth chapter Kelp-Stebbins examines the work of Haida artist Michael Nicoll Yahgulanaas. Eschewing the term comics Yahgulanaas has developed a Haida manga specifically as a rejection of "the settler tradition of North America" (p. 156). Kelp-Stebbins argues "that Yahgulanaas's work can and should be read for how it cultivates cultural difference as technical practice. No mere synthesis of two cultures, Yahgulanaas's art compels a reader to question and rethink ways of seeing, reading, and knowing, while simultaneously highlighting points of disjuncture or untranslatability in modes of discourse and inscription" (p. 155). The chapter proceeds from this premise to use Yahgulanaas's work to interrogate the spaces of comics, reveal underlying ideologies in their production, circulation, and reception, and challenge some shop-worn concepts about art and literature.

Kelp-Stebbins final chapter examines the Lebanese comic *Samandal*. As with her earlier chapters Kelp-Stebbins situates her subject within a potted history of the conditions of its publication. The colonial history of Lebanon, the Civil War, and the type of city Beirut is, all shape *Samandal* in distinctive ways. Published in three languages — Arabic, French, and English — *Samandal* has an in betweenness and offers picture stories as a descriptor since there is no one Arabic word for comics. *Samandal's* in betweenness was underscored materially in the first fifteen published issues by the need to reorient oneself while reading to match the reading direction of

the language with Arabic being marked by dextrosinistrality. In this manner *Samandal* is “a radical reimagining of how to physically foreground relations of translation and untranslatability” (p. 207). Kelp-Stebbins finds that *Samandal* brings together the various tensions and relations in comics that Charles Hatfield has classified — “the interplay between word and image, between single panel and sequence, between sequence and surface, and between text as object and text as experience.” By requiring readers to flip a page to achieve the required reading direction *Samandal* heightens the image-text tension (p. 216). For Kelp-Stebbins *Samandal* flips more than the page and challenges readers and comic studies to find better reading modalities.

In her acknowledgements Kelp-Stebbins describes Comics Studies as “a male-dominated field” (p. xiv). This book shows that, while the majority of older folks in the field may well be men, the future belongs to the many women who have published stellar books in recent years with presses like the Ohio State University Press.¹

¹ In this regard be sure to see reviews by Eszter Szép’s review of the book in *Afterimage*, Vol. 50, Number 1, 2023: pp. 73–78 and Chunwei Liu, “Mapping World Comics.” *The Comics Grid: Journal of Comics Scholarship*, 12(1) 2022: pp. 1–8. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.16995/cg.9708>